

Proposed Marketing Strategy to Increase Brand Awareness for Coffee Shop Business (Case Study on Brand Payu Coffee & Eatery)

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ABSTRACT: The total distribution of Coffee in Indonesia is increasing every year, and it is in line with the growing of Coffee Shop industry in Indonesia, specifically in Jakarta. Payu is one of local SME Coffee Shop brand located in Gandaria, South Jakarta which was established in 2020. Building brand awareness is important for a new brand, particularly for SME company with an existence of less than five years like Payu. According to interview with Payu's co-owner that Payu brand awareness is very low which in line with the result of questionnaire from total of 202 respondents shows that 68,8% never heard of Payu before. To analyse the root caused more deeply, researchers used Fishbone Diagram and Inter-relationship Diagram and found that Lack of Marketing effort is primary root cause for Payu. The purpose of this research is to propose a suitable marketing strategy to increase Brand Awareness for Coffee Shops like Payu. Researchers use both quantitative and qualitative methodologies in conducting research. Data collection is done by conducting in-depth interview, distributing questionnaires, and conducting a focus group discussion. The collected data is then used to do analysis based on the collection methods. Quantitative results are used to make Cluster Analysis and Brand Awareness Analysis. While Qualitative results is used to make Behavioural Shift analysis and Brand Concept Mapping. According to focus group discussion, customers are like the coffee trends like Ready-to-Drink Coffee and Snapchilled Coffee. After conducting analysis, the proposed marketing strategies are carried out. Based on BCM model, Payu are relatable with associations links "Nyaman" and "Kerja". There are three new marketing strategies that can increase coffee shops brand awareness like Payu. First, developing Buyer Persona Creation strategy based on cluster analysis. Second, coffee shops can work with influencers who has audience driven from the Buyer Persona Creation strategy. Third, conduct a brand activation based on the association links from brand concept mapping and invite the chosen influencers.

KEYWORDS: Brand Awareness, Marketing Strategy, Coffee Shop, Buyer Persona Creation, Influencer Marketing, Brand Activation.

INTRODUCTION

In 2022/2023, Indonesia's coffee production will rise 7% to 11.35 million (60 kg) bags. Domestic coffee consumption is expected to reach 4.8 million bags in 2022/23 when pandemic restrictions are removed. Indonesia ranks below Brazil, Vietnam, and Colombia in coffee output. 67% of production is exported, 33% is consumed domestically (Rahmanulloh, A., 2022). Means this situation explains how Indonesia can increase its national economy through the coffee industry, and we agreed that coffee is an industry with great opportunities in Indonesia, particularly in major cities like Jakarta.

Fajrillah et al. (2020) state external company challenges may be well-predicted and well-handled or vice versa. The business owner's comfort zone is also not guaranteed. The present scenario shows covid 19 Pandemic. The virus' quick spread has affected several companies, including the coffee shop. Coffee shop owners must resist external challenges. Many coffee merchants and coffee shop entrepreneurs dying in Jakarta, another pandemic-stricken city. The business owners demanded improvements after recent cases. It is essential for growth and profitability. South Jakarta has 250-300 coffee shops, a large quantity for 1 municipality. It rises 10 to 15% year, making competition fiercer (Wartakota, 2018). Even if the trend and quantity of coffee consumers in South Jakarta are large, this region is considered a red ocean.

Figure 1. Brand Awareness Result

According to **Figure 1**, 68.8% of 202 respondents did not know PAYU. More than half have never heard of PAYU. Payu exclusively sells items & services offline, yet they use Instagram for social media promotion. Because sales are stable, businesses enter a comfort zone without a new marketing strategy. Low brand awareness will be business issue in this paper. Payu should improve the situation. The research objective is to propose Marketing Strategies for Coffee Shop Owners like Payu for increasing company’s Brand Awareness. Because of that, researcher is interested in examining Coffee Shop industry particularly in South Jakarta and can suggesting to Coffee Shops owner how to increase brand awareness with several new marketing strategies which will be discussed in detail in next chapter.

Figure 2. Payu Fishbone Diagram

In above figure 2 is root cause diagram of Payu, it is a tool or method that helps researchers to find out the root cause of a business issue as well and find out what is the best solution for the issue. Researchers also obtaining an Inter-Relationship diagram to knowing deeper and conclude that “Lack of Marketing effort/channel” is the root cause of Low Brand Awareness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Brand Awareness

The level to which consumers are familiar with a brand and its goods is directly correlated with the effectiveness of the brand in communicating specific signals and memories and at making its unique selling points known to consumers (Keller, 2013). The

ability of consumers to recall and mentally categorize a brand as a preferred option is known as "brand awareness." There are four stages of brand awareness according to Hermawan (2010): Unaware of Brand, Brand Recognition, Brand Recall, Top of Mind.

Brand Concept Mapping

Table 1. Aggregation Rules of Brand Concept Mapping

Step	Measures	Rules
1. Select core brand associations	Frequency of mention Number of interconnections	Select brand associations that are <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Included on at least 50% of maps. •Included on 45%–49% of maps if the number of connections the number of connections for core associations we identified previously.
2. Select first-order brand associations	Frequency of first-order mentions Ratio of first-order mentions Type of interconnections	Select core brand associations that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Have a ratio of first-order mentions to total mentions of at least 50%. •Have more superordinate than subordinate interconnections.
3. Select core brand association links	Frequencies for association links	Select core brand association links by <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Finding inflection point on frequency plot. •Inflection point = target number. •Including all association links that appear on or above the target number of maps.
4. Select non-core brand association links	Frequencies for association links	Select non-core brand association links that are <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Linked to a core brand association. •Linked on or above the target number of maps.
5. Select number of connecting lines	Mean number of lines used per link	Select single, double, or triple lines for each brand association link by <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Determining the mean number of lines used per link. •Rounding up or down to the next integer number (e.g., 2.3 = 2).

Cluster Analysis

When user say "k-means clustering," k stands for the number of groups. Most of the time, users don't know the value of k ahead of time, so users have to choose it anyway. The centroid of each cluster is usually found by taking the average of the feature vectors in that cluster. Under the k-means clustering algorithm, each data point is put into a cluster based on the cluster center that is closest to it. Since the centroids can't be calculated directly until the clusters are made, the user sets k initial values for the centroids at the start of the clustering process. Once clusters are formed, the true centroid values may be determined. Once clusters have been made, the real values for the centroid are found.

Buyer Persona Creation

A buyer persona is a fictionalized, generalized representation of your ideal, most comprehensive target customers. A customer profile often consists of both objective (such as age, location, and income) and subjective (such as interests, motivations, and concerns) data. For your convenience, buyer personas are sometimes offered as a condensed overview of this demographic and psychographic data, along with a made-up name and (stock picture) appearance (Kumar, B, 2022).

Influencer

"Digital Influencers" are trend professionals who keep themselves occupied by, among other things, blogging, Instagramming, and videoblogging (Andrian, 2018). Customers provide content on social media showing how they use a product. They earn profits via partnerships with other companies. Influencers have great potential for businesses, as they can quickly communicate information about the goods and services supplied by these companies to their massive audiences of followers.

Influencer Endorsement

Influencer Endorsement is an activity to promote a product to be offered to potential customers in order for potential customers to buy and use the product. Entrepreneurs use influencer services so that the products they make may reach a larger audience and so that they can earn money from each product sale (Ridha, 2018). Success in business may be "boosted" with the use of influencer services.

Social Media Influencer

"Social media influencers" are individuals who have a large number of online followers and who utilize such platforms to spread news and opinions (Duffy, 2020). The ultimate objective of every social media influencer, Alves de Castro, O'Reilly, and Carthy (2021), is to influence every aspect of their audience's lives.

Nano Influencer

It is a new kind of influencer with a smaller fan base than micro-influencers. These individuals have a great deal of influence in their local communities and neighborhoods. It is possible that these people have considerable influence on their close circle of friends and acquaintances. The disadvantage of having a relatively small audience remains, despite the high level of engagement (Ismail, 2018). According to Bughin et al. (2010), nano-influencers are the most effective influencers to capture the possibility of reaching out to people in a more organic and genuine approach.

Brand Activation

Brand Activation, although not a theory, is a method for evaluating brands (Morel et al., 2002). One key aspect of brand activation that contributes to brand satisfaction and trust in a brand is the quality of the brand activation (Marist et al., 2014). According to Ajzen's (1992) Persuasive Communication Theory, a trust and loyal customer base may be built with the use of promotional marketing materials that are persuasive in nature. Marketing communications theories provide an explanation for brand activation, elaborating on how it influences consumers to react to a marketing message via the content of specific brand activation activities (Marist et al., 2014; Mu, 2017).

How Influencer Marketing Shifts Brand Awareness

Conclusions that may be derived from the findings and discussions thus far include the following:

1. To begin, the most effective kind of advertising in the present day is social media advertising, which is mostly accessible through mobile devices.
2. Second, social media influencer marketing is a kind of advertising.
3. Thirdly, promotional costs may be cut in half or more by using influencer marketing.
4. The application of Influencer Marketing is very suitable for improving brand image effectively and improving Brand Awareness of consumers to the brand.

Hariyanti, N. T., & Wirapraja, A. (2018)

Conceptual Framework

The concept starts from the left, which is yellow, which are 3 factors that influenced the main objective of this research, namely increasing brand awareness of Payu Coffee & Eatery. The 3 factors are Behavioural shift, Brand Activation, and Influencer marketing. 2 factors are directly proportional to the problems that exist in the related Coffee Shop, meaning that if the researcher can combine the three properly and correctly, increasing brand activation plus influencer marketing will result in increased brand awareness as well (blue on the top side of figure II.). While 1 factor which Behavioural Shifts is directly related to product adjustment and affecting brand awareness as well.

Figure 3. Conceptual framework

METHODOLOGY

Data Collection

Researchers are using a concurrent triangulation technique that enables them to do both quantitative and qualitative research independently. Because of this, the researcher hopes to provide a detailed account of all the study data gathered here. The researcher also uses primary and secondary data. This chapter will explain the study's methodology, please see figure III.1 below.

Figure 4. Classification of Marketing Research Data

This study used a mixed-method approach, meaning that the primary data utilized both qualitative and quantitative data. Before diving into the more analytical part of the study, researchers do qualitative data research to get an understanding of the subject at issue. Qualitative methods include a wide range of techniques for collecting both direct and indirect data for research. These Qualitative data are collected directly through in-depth interviews to know more about internal marketing in an organization that can impact brand awareness. And followed by focus group discussions to get more information for chapter IV. Researchers apply a thorough screening procedure using these criteria to everyone who will be interviewed for this research.

Table 2. Respondents Criteria

Candidate	Criteria	QTY	Method
Internal Payu Team	Have a Role and Responsibility for Sales and Marketing	1	In-Depth Interview
Coffee Shop Consumers	Have tried 5 coffee shops (Direct Competitors): Mineral Cafe, Kopi Perempuan Tani, Suasanakopi, Kopi Muja, and Payu Coffee & Eatery itself.	6	Focus Group Discussion

Additionally, quantitative data is gathered from individual respondents to get their take on the factors proposed in problem exploration. Researchers want to validate the level of brand awareness of the company with this quantitative data analysis. Secondary data, which differs somewhat from the primary data described above, is used to complement the research and improve Payu's future findings. Researchers divided secondary data into only one category. The technique is called a literature review and involves extracting useful information from books, most of which are about marketing.

RESEARCH DESIGN

Research design serves as a kind of road map for carrying out marketing research projects; they lay out the steps that must be taken to gather the data that will be used to create hypotheses and draw conclusions (Malhotra, 2007). Both exploratory and conclusive research strategies exist. The objective of this study is to investigate something in order to learn more about it and have a better understanding on the issue. In this case, exploratory research is used to provide preliminary hypotheses or insights, guide any necessary follow-up studies, and pinpoint areas where further information is required. (Aaker et al, 2007; Malhotra, 2007).

Figure 5. Research Design

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Cluster Analysis

In this research, the k-means technique was used to do the cluster members' grouping in a non-hierarchical method. Based on their similarity, K-means will classify things into distinct categories. The researchers here employed a total of 4 clusters in their analysis. Furthermore, an ANOVA test was carried out to determine the significance of the effect of each variable on the grouping of 4 clusters. After forming several clusters from the respondents, the next step is to look for the characteristics of each cluster formed. The following is a table of characteristics of each cluster.

Table 3. Characteristics of each Cluster

Cluster	Gender	Umur	Pekerjaan	Domisili	Pendapatan	Minuman Favorit	Peminum Kopi	Konsumsi Kopi dalam 1 Minggu	Ketersediaan Membayar 1 Gelas Kopi	Kedai Kopi yang Diketahui	Pengetahuan tentang "PAYU"
Cluster 1	Pria	18-24	Pelajar / Mahasiswa	DKI Jakarta	Rp 1.500.000 - 5.000.000	Kopi	Ya	3-5 gelas	Rp 20.000 - 30.000	Starbucks	Mungkin
Cluster 2	Wanita	25-34	Profesional / Mahasiswa	DKI Jakarta	Rp 5.000.000 - 10.000.000	Juice	Lumayan	5-10 gelas	Rp 30.000 - 40.000	Fore	Ya

Cluster 3	Pria	25-34	Pegawai Swasta	DKI Jakarta	Rp 5.000.000 - 10.000.000	Kopi	Ya	3-5 gelas	Rp 30.000 - 40.000	Tuku	Ya
Cluster 4	Wanita	25-34	Wirasaha	DKI Jakarta	Rp 11.000.000 - 20.000.000	Kopi	Ya	3-5 gelas	Rp 40.000 - 50.000	Starbucks, Nako, Flash	Ya

Based on **Table 2** above, the characteristics for each cluster are as follows.

Clusters 1

Men aged around 18 to 24 years with student work, domiciled in the DKI Jakarta area. Income per month is IDR 1,500,000 – IDR 5,000,000. Favorite drink is coffee and is a coffee drinker. In one week can spend 3 to 5 cups of coffee. Their willingness to pay for one glass of coffee is IDR 20,000 – IDR 30,000,000. The most known coffee shop is Starbucks. Their impression of the PAYU logo is artistic and they find out information about PAYU from word of mouth or hearing from relatives or close friends.

Clusters 2

Women aged around 25 to 34 years with student work, domiciled in the DKI Jakarta area. Income per month is IDR 5,000,000 – IDR 10,000,000. Favorite drink is juice and quite a coffee drinker. In one week can spend 5 to 10 cups of coffee. Their willingness to pay for one glass of coffee is IDR 30,000 – IDR 40,000,000. The most known coffee shop is Fore. Their impression of the PAYU logo is artistic and they find out information about PAYU from word of mouth or hearing from relatives or close friends.

Clusters 3

Men aged around 25 to 34 years with private employees, domiciled in the DKI Jakarta area. Income per month is IDR 5,000,000 – IDR 10,000,000. Favorite drink is coffee and coffee drinkers. In one week can spend 3 to 5 cups of coffee. Their willingness to pay for one glass of coffee is IDR 30,000 – IDR 40,000,000. The most known coffee shop is Tuku. Their impression of the PAYU logo is hard to link with coffee and find out information about PAYU from word of mouth or hearing from relatives or close friends.

Clusters 4

Women aged around 25 to 34 years with entrepreneurs, with domiciles in the DKI Jakarta area. Income per month is IDR 11,000,000 – IDR 20,000,000. Favorite drink is coffee and coffee drinkers. In one week can spend 3 to 5 cups of coffee. Their willingness to pay for one glass of coffee is IDR 40,000 – IDR 50,000,000. The best known coffee shops are Starbucks, Nako, and Flash. Their impression of the PAYU logo is hard to link with coffee and find out information about PAYU from word of mouth or hearing from relatives or close friends.

Behavioural Shift (Product Adjustment)

On the results of focus group discussion related to coffee trends and behavioural shifts in the coffee industry, each participant has a different perspective. There are those who have a similar perspective where they discuss ready to drink coffee which has become a trend lately. There are also those who have the perspective that “kopi susu gula aren” and ice cream coffee are hype trends. Meanwhile, some say that the trend of carbonated coffee is entering Indonesia at a moment. And others such as litre coffee, coffee mocktails, and cold brew as they saw it as a behavioural shifting. However, interestingly, with different perspectives on this coffee trend, all participants agreed and were interested in Ready to Drink coffee and Snapchilled coffee products (Gunter, M., 2022). Participant feedback tends to be positive with answers dominated by “Interest, like, relevant, cool, OK, suitable, interesting”. 2 participants had a perspective that the coffee shop market nowadays is much more intelligent. There are also those who say as long as it's good for content, meaning it's relevant to today's market.

The conclusion is that product adjustments in coffee shops such as Ready-to-drink coffee and Snap-chilled coffee in the coffee shop industry can make coffee shops more attractive which causes increased brand awareness.

Brand Concept Mapping

Step 1 and 2 - BCM

Table 4. BCM Measures for Payu

No	Brand Associations	Core Associations		First-Order Associations			
		Frequency of Mention	Number of Interconnections	Frequency of First-Order Mention	Ratio of First-Order Mention (%)	Subordinate Connections	Super-ordinate Connections
1	<i>Kopi</i>	16	17	11	68.8	12	5
2	<i>Coffee</i>	13	17	10	76.9	11	6
3	Cocok	11	12	5	45.5	9	3
4	<i>Temen</i>	8	9	6	75.0	6	3
5	Trend	7	6	3	42.9	4	2
6	<i>Nyaman</i>	7	8	5	71.4	6	2
7	Enak	7	7	3	42.9	4	3
8	<i>Chilled</i>	4	4	2	50.0	3	1
9	Sat Set	4	3	1	25.0	3	0
10	Interest	4	9	1	25.0	8	1
11	<i>Meeting</i>	4	5	2	50.0	3	2x
12	<i>Kerja</i>	4	3	2	50.0	1	2
13	Suka	3	8	5	166.7	4	4
14	Seger	3	7	3	100.0	4	3
15	Pas	3	4	2	66.7	3	1
16	Tengah	3	2	1	33.3	1	1
17	Bagus	3	3	2	66.7	1	2
18	Nongkrong	3	12	5	166.7	9	3
19	Nugas	3	3	1	33.3	2	1
20	Strategis	3	5	2	66.7	3	2
21	Aesthetic	2	4	2	100.0	4	0
22	Laris	1	3	1	100.0	2	1

Notes: N = 5 participants. Core brand associations are in bold, and first-order brand associations are in bold italics.

Step 3 and 4 - BCM

The remaining major brand associations were plotted by researchers. They had to link to one of the core brand associations, and the consensus map had to highlight the connections between the 12 core brand associations. In order to achieve this, researchers first counted the frequency of connections between various relationships in various maps. The number of unique association linkages recorded on a single map, two maps, three maps, etc., was then counted and categorized by frequency. Figure 5 displays the distribution of the number of maps on which each of the 28 different association connections occurred (28 different links on one

map, 27 different links on two maps, 17 different links on three maps, etc.). These occurrences only reflect bidirectional relationships between associations; most possible ties between associations were never shown on a single map.

Analysis of Brand Association Links for Payu Coffee & Eatery

Figure 6. Brand Association Link Analysis

Researchers utilized these frequencies to decide which of the many possible connection linkages to include in the consensus map, prioritizing those with dramatically elevated frequency counts on the underlying graphs (inflection point). Figure 5 shows that the number five serves as an inflection point, and that this number served as the criteria for which core association linkages should be included in the final consensus brand map. To finish this stage, researcher used a consensus map to create 12 connections between core brand associations.

Step 5 - BCM

In this step, the BCM consensus already made and clear that Payu has 6 core brand associations and researcher chose 2 words that have the most interlinks between associations which “Nyaman” and “Kerja”. Therefore, these 2 words will be further elaborated in the proposed solution chapter

Figure 7. Consensus Brand Concept Mapping of Payu

PROPOSED MARKETING STRATEGIES

Marketing Strategy based on Cluster Analysis

1. Buyer Persona Creation

This solution is formed as the output of the Cluster Analysis, and it is shown in the cluster characteristics table that there are four clusters, but researchers only chose two clusters that have differences that can be used as a reference for Buyer Persona Creation by researchers. Visualizing buyer personas will help Payu Social Media influencers and potential customers understand what each persona needs. Based on the cluster analysis that was already talked about above, the results for each group are shown in the next section. There are certain pieces of information in each persona, such as: The name of each persona, Characteristics, Scenario, Social profile, Product Orientation, Motivation, Goals.

Persona 1 - The Benefit Seeker

Figure 8. The Benefit Seeker Type Persona

The benefit seeker is the persona type that is shown in figure 7. They are between 18 - 24 years old. This kind is characterized by the desire to get the most possible advantages from offline purchases of coffee items. They are typically a male who needs 3 - 5 cups of coffee weekly. This benefit seeker can spend in a range from 20.000 to 30.000 rupiah for a cup of coffee. They believe that if they go to the shop, the baristas will provide them with information on the discounts, promotions, events, and products that are available.

Figure 9. The Real Experience Seeker Type Persona

The real experience seeker is the persona type that best describes this scenario (figure 8). They are between 25 - 34 years old. Because seeing the goods for themselves is the most significant aspect of the buying process for them, they choose to purchase a cup of coffee or coffee products via a channel that is not online. They are females who need 5 - 10 cups of coffee in a straight week and can spend up to 40.000 rupiah for a cup of coffee. In addition, since they do not have a complete understanding of the product, which is why they go to the shop, the Baristas there may provide them with an explanation.

Table 5. Summary of all persona types

No	Persona Name	Key Point (Differentiation)	Similarity
1	Muhammad Alex (The Benefit Seeker)	Younger, Low income. Going to the store will get more benefits than an online channel, such as knowing the promotion and detailed information from Baristas. Low spending.	Coffee Drinkers Same domicile
2	Nadya Raline (The Real Experience Seeker)	More Mature, Medium income. The important thing is to see the product directly before buying it. Higher willingness to pay and coffee consumption.	Both Student

Marketing Strategy based on Brand Concept Mapping

2. Influencer Marketing

Step 1 – Influencer Marketing

The first thing that has to be done in this strategy is to choose individuals who are considered to be influential, in short choosing the right influencers. Based on INSG.co regarding Influencer Marketing, Nano-Influencers is strong in Indonesia, and they specifically conclude that Nano-Influencers is suitable for the Food & Beverages Industry in Indonesia.

Table 6. Suitable Influencers for Indonesian Market

Type of influencer content	Most popular influencer tier
Fashion & Beauty	Nano-influencers (38%)
Entertainment	Micro-influencers (37%)
Food & Drink	Nano-influencers (54%)

Nano Influencers & Micro-Influencers are strong in Indonesia

It is indicated in the Buyer Persona Creation that there will be a total of two personas that will be publicized and suggested to Payu by the researcher. Whereas in this chapter, the selection of influencers will also be elaborated on by the two personas, researchers believe that the influencers that are to be selected must have an audience or target market that is aligned with the characteristics of the persona that was analyzed in Buyer Persona Creation before this one. The short meaning is that the selection of influencers has to be driven by the development of persona in order to ensure that the process of targeting Payu's audience proceeds smoothly and that the output of increasing brand awareness may be as effective as it possibly can be. So, researchers think it would be very ideal if researchers can provide two nano-influencers for both personas. Meaning that would be 4 influencers in this section, please see below:

1st Persona → The Benefit Seeker @javafoodie (Dadad Sesa) and @foodventurer_ (Prawnche)

Figure 10. The Benefit Seeker Nano-Influencer

If you're looking for a comprehensive guide to the cuisine of Java, particularly that of Jakarta and Bogor, his Instagram account is your best option. Dadad is a well-known food blogger, and as such, he has visited several eateries. The vast majority of his work consists of Reels, making it simple to promote to a broader audience. Payu fits in with Dadad's target demographic. And yes, Prawnche is his actual given name. The fact that Prawn evaluates and makes all the foods he like suggests that he was born to enjoy them. The food photographs on his Instagram feed are really close up, so tread carefully. The Chinese version of NPR and Australia's TheRiotACT are just two of the many foreign news outlets that have profiled him. Prawn will never just suggest a meal without first providing an honest assessment of it. The researcher thinks he can quickly increase brand awareness in Payu.

2nd Persona → The Real Experience Seeker @cnlulaby (Cindy Lulaby) and @justtryandtaste (Endang Indriani)

Figure 11. The Real Experience Seeker Nano-Influencer

Cindy Lulaby is the best option since the researcher needs more than simply a food blogger. She writes critiques on every kind of Indonesian and Jakartan food. Cindy has sampled every kind of fast food possible, from burgers and ice cream to chicken katsu. She entered the food industry by way of the blog Lulaby Spoon. If you easily become hungry, you may want to avoid her Instagram profile. Cindy's passion for blogging extends beyond only cuisine to include sharing her joyous life events with her friends and family. If you want to target regular food lovers in Indonesia, Cindy is the kind of relaxed and aesthetically pleasing cafe hopper. A tranquil, optimistic, and physically active way of life is what Endang, a person of influence, finds most appealing. Take a peek at her page and you'll see that she's all about healthy eating with recipes for you to try, pictures of her garden, and a cat. That's right; she takes equal pleasure in managing her garden. Many companies in the healthy food industry have formed sponsorship partnerships in an effort to benefit from this perception. Researchers think she may help raise awareness for the Payu brand since her personality meshes nicely with the company's.

Step 2 – Influencer Marketing

The second step that has to be carried out in this part is to conduct an appropriate content briefing for the influencers who were chosen in step 1. It was indicated in Behavioral Shift (product adjustment) that the trend toward "Ready to Drink" and "Snapchilled" coffee is a very fascinating one. This trend was discussed. Participants are willing to pay a premium price for material on social media because it is seen to have a high level of aesthetic value for content. And in the study of Brand Concept Mapping, it is indicated that the phrases "Nyaman" and "Kerja" are the words that have the greatest interlinks between them. This indicates that in order to optimize brand awareness, a strategy that is right on target must be carried out. One such strategy involves conducting briefs to influencers in order to promote or highlight the brand association "Nyaman" and "Kerja," and it is expected that this will optimize the content marketing strategy. Influencers can also highlight the words from links between core brand associations and first-order brand associations like "Nyaman buat kerja tempatnya" or "Coffee Shop yang cocok untuk lunch-meeting".

3. Brand Activation

The third proposed solution are to use brand activation as a tool to increase brand awareness. The same applies to Influencer Marketing, which is discussed in detail above. This chapter digs further into the concept of influencer marketing and establishes connections between related concepts by organizing an Influencer Marketing Workshop Event at Payu Coffee & Eatery over the course of four days and including four unique & different nano-influencers. One influencer will attend over the course of two weekends, and everyone will get to mingle and connect (Saturday and Sunday).

The event's focus on product adjustment, in this case, "Ready to drinks" and "Snapchilled" coffee will generate brand activation. The researchers brand concept mapping will also play a role in shaping the strategy, particularly as it focuses on the most interlinked core brand association the words "Nyaman" and "Kerja" and their relative importance to consumers. Because of this, researchers developed the following brand activation schedule for Payu as below:

Table 7. Brand Activation Schedule

Day	Topics / Workshops	Influencers
1	Topic: How to make Ready to Drink Coffee with a good bean from Nusantara	@javafoodie
	Embrace your comfy with Payu Coffee	@cnlulaby
2	Topic: Snapchilled, why not?	@foodventurer_
	WFC friendly only in Payu Coffee	@justtryandtaste

CONCLUSION

This paper is intended to assist Payu Coffee & Eatery in resolving business issue with low in Brand Awareness. It is clear from Fishbone Diagram and Inter-relationship Diagram that the primary root cause of Low Brand Awareness is "Lack of Marketing effort / channels".

By utilizing competitor analysis, cluster analysis, and brand concept mapping, Payu internal team can gain an overview of the mix of customers perspectives and owner's capabilities using in-depth interviews, focus group discussion, and survey questionnaire to overcome this business issue. As a result of this research, three proposed marketing strategies are suggested to increase brand awareness of Payu based on the conceptual Framework which Buyer Persona Creation, Influencer Marketing, and Brand Activation.

All the proposed strategies are elaborated based on all analysis researchers already done. The researchers projected that by putting these ideas into practice, Payu's brand awareness would increase.

By this research also, researchers hope to be able to help all coffee shop owners in Jakarta or Indonesia who have the same business issue so they can implement the proposed marketing strategies that the researchers have already made. As for the next researchers can continue and further research as well.

REFERENCES

1. Alves de Castro, Charles & O'Reilly, Isobel & Carthy, Aiden. (2021). Social Media Influencers (SMIs) in Context: A Literature Review. *Journal of Marketing Management*. 9. 59-71. 10.15640/jmm.v9n2a9.
2. Andrian, D. (2018, 14). Pengertian dan Jenis Influencer Marketing. Retrieved from whello.id.
3. Brandt, C., de Mortanges, C. City branding: A brand concept map analysis of a university town. *Place Brand Public Dipl* 7, 50–63 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1057/pb.2010.37>
4. Duffy, Brooke. (2020). Social Media Influencers. 1-4. 10.1002/9781119429128.iegmc219.
5. Fajrillah, Purba. S, dll. 2020. Smart Entrepreneurship: Peluang Bisnis Kreatif & Inovatif di Era Digital. Yayasan Kita Menulis.
6. Gunter, M., 2022, 10 Coffee Consumer Trends to Know in 2022. Indonesia: Coffee Affection.
7. Hariyanti, N. T., & Wirapraja, A. (2018). Pengaruh Influencer Marketing Sebagai Strategi Pemasaran Digital Era Moderen (Sebuah Studi Literatur). *Jurnal Eksekutif*, 15(1), 133–146
8. Huang Z. Extensions to the k-means algorithm for clustering large data sets with categorical values. *Data Mining Knowledge Discovery*. 2(2): 283–304. 1998.
9. Ismail, K., (2020). "Social Media Influencers: Mega, Macro, Micro Or Nano". [online] CMSWire.com. Available at: <https://www.cmswire.com/digital-marketing/social-media-influencers-mega-macro-micro-or-nano/>
10. Keller, K. L. (2013). *Strategic brand management: building, measuring, and managing brand equity* (4th ed). Boston: Pearson
11. K. Teknomo. K-Mean Clustering Code in Matlab. http://people.revoledu.com/kardi/tutorial/kMean/matlab_kMeans.htm. 2006.
12. Kumar, B., 2022, Know your Customer: How to build your buyer Personas. US: Shopify.
13. Mackenzie, 2022, Step-by-step Guide to Defining your Buyer Personas. Washington: Evenbound.
14. Malhotra, Naresh, 2007. *Marketing Research : an applied orientation*, pearson education, inc., fifth edition. New Jersey : USA
15. Marist, A. I., Yuliati, L. N., & Najib, M. (2014). The Role of Event in Building Brand Satisfaction, Trust and Loyalty of Isotonic Drink. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 6(6), 57-66.
16. Morel, P., Preisler, P., & Nyström, A. (2002). Brand activation. *Starsky Insight*. Retrieved from <http://easylink.terki.no/index.php/content/content/download/159/699/version/file/13BrandActivation.pdf>
17. Rahmanulloh, A., 2022, USDA: Coffee Annual-Indonesia. Available from: <https://www.fas.usda.gov/data/indonesia-coffee-annual-6> [Accessed on November 3, 2022].
18. Ridha, A. (2018). Celebrity Endorser Pada Jejaring Sosial Instagram Untuk Menarik Minat Pembelian Calon Konsumen. *Journal Economic Resources*
19. Statista, 2022, Coffee-Indonesia. Available from: <https://www.statista.com/outlook/cmo/hot-drinks/coffee/indonesia> [Accessed on November 2, 2022].
20. Taslaud, G., 2022, Top 10 Food Influencers in Indonesia in 2022. Available from: <https://www.insg.co/en/food-influencer-indonesia/> [Accessed on November 29, 2022].
21. Zenker, S. Measuring place brand equity with the advanced Brand Concept Map (aBCM) method. *Place Brand Public Dipl* 10, 158–166 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1057/pb.2014.2>

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